

Supplemental Table

Table S1 Identification, hemolysis type, and antibiotic resistance profiles of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) strains isolated from camel milk.

Note: R = *Lactococcus lactis*; C = *Leuconostoc mesenteroides*; TET = tetracycline; CIP = ciprofloxacin; E = erythromycin; VAN = vancomycin; “-” = not detected.

Sample Location	Sample Type	Medium	Identification	Strain ID	Hemolysis	Antibiotic Resistance
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R1	γ	TET
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R2	γ	CIP, TET
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R3	γ	TET
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R4	α	TET
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R5	γ	TET
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R6	γ	TET
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R7	α	TET
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R8	γ	TET
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R9	γ	TET
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R10	γ	TET
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R11	γ	TET
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R12	γ	CIP, TET
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R13	γ	TET
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R14	γ	TET
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R15	γ	TET
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R16	γ	TET
Bussreti	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R17	γ	S
Bussreti	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R18	γ	TET, CIP
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R19	γ	S
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R20	γ	CIP, E ^e
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R21	γ	S
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R22	γ	S
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Lactococcus lactis</i>	R23	γ	S
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	C1	γ	VAN
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	C2	γ	VAN
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	C3	γ	CIP, VAN ^f
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	C4	γ	VAN
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	C5	γ	VAN
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	C6	γ	VAN
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	C7	γ	CIP, VAN
Sangonghe	Fermented	SL	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	C8	γ	VAN
Sangonghe	Fermented	SL	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	C9	γ	VAN
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	C10	γ	VAN
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	C11	γ	VAN
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Leuconostoc mesenteroides</i>	C12	γ	CIP, VAN
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>	Z1	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>	Z2	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>	Z3	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>	Z4	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>	Z5	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	SL	<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>	Z6	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>	Z7	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>	Z8	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>	Z9	-	-

Sample Location	Sample Type	Medium	Identification	Strain ID	Hemolysis	Antibiotic Resistance
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	F1	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	F2	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	F3	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	F4	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	F5	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	F6	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	F7	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	F8	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	F9	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	F10	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	SL	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	F11	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	SL	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	F12	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	SL	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	F13	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	SL	<i>Lactobacillus fermentum</i>	F14	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Lactobacillus paracasei</i>	FG1	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Lactobacillus paracasei</i>	FG2	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Lactobacillus paracasei</i>	FG3	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Lactobacillus paracasei</i>	FG4	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Lactobacillus paracasei</i>	FG5	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Lactobacillus paracasei</i>	FG6	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus gasseri</i>	G1	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Lactobacillus gasseri</i>	G2	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Ligilactobacillus salivarius</i>	T1	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Ligilactobacillus salivarius</i>	T2	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Weissella confusa</i>	W1	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	SL	<i>Weissella confusa</i>	W2	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	SL	<i>Weissella confusa</i>	W3	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Weissella confusa</i>	W4	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Weissella confusa</i>	W5	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Weissella confusa</i>	W6	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Weissella confusa</i>	W7	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Weissella confusa</i>	W8	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Weissella confusa</i>	W9	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Weissella confusa</i>	W10	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Weissella confusa</i>	W11	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Enterococcus Durans</i>	N1	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Enterococcus Durans</i>	N2	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Weissella cibaria</i>	S1	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Weissella cibaria</i>	S2	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Weissella cibaria</i>	S3	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Weissella cibaria</i>	S4	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Weissella cibaria</i>	S5	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	SL	<i>Weissella cibaria</i>	S6	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	SL	<i>Weissella cibaria</i>	S7	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Pediococcusacidilactici</i>	RSP1	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Pediococcusacidilactici</i>	RSP2	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Pediococcusacidilactici</i>	RSP3	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Pediococcusacidilactici</i>	RSP4	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC1	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC2	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC3	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC4	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC5	-	-

Sample Location	Sample Type	Medium	Identification	Strain ID	Hemolysis	Antibiotic Resistance
Xiajiahar	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC6	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC7	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC8	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC9	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC10	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC11	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC12	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC13	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC14	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC15	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC16	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC17	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC18	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC19	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC20	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC21	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC22	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC23	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC24	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC25	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC26	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC27	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC28	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC29	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC30	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC31	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC32	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC33	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC34	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC35	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC36	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC37	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC38	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC39	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC40	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC41	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC42	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC43	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC44	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC45	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC46	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC47	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC48	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC49	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC50	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC51	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC52	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC53	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC54	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC55	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC56	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC57	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC58	-	-

Sample Location	Sample Type	Medium	Identification	Strain ID	Hemolysis	Antibiotic Resistance
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC59	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC60	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC61	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC62	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC63	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC64	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC65	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC66	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC67	-	-
Sangonghe	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC68	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC69	-	-
Bussreti	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC70	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	SC71	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	SL	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG1	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG2	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG3	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG4	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG5	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG6	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG7	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG8	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG9	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG10	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG11	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG12	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG13	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG14	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG15	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG16	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG17	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG18	-	-
Xiajiahar	Fresh	MRS	<i>Enterococcus thailandicus</i>	TG19	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	RS1	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	RS2	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	RS3	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	RS4	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	RS5	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	RS6	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	RS7	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	RS8	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	RS9	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	RS10	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	RS11	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	RS12	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	RS13	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	RS14	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	RS15	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	RS16	-	-
Sangonghe	Fermented	MRS	<i>Lactobacillus helveticus</i>	RS17	-	-